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πεδίο

Children, adolescents and social networking in Cyprus: the evolution of the relationship and its re-definition

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Social Networking is among the most common everyday activities of all ages. The users are counting in millions, which gives to Social Networks (SN) the power to influence social structures, institutions and the relations that run them. The purpose of this work is to re-approach the matter and to investigate whether children and adolescents in Cyprus use these networks for the same reasons mentioned in the bibliography or if there has been a change. The sample constituted of 101 boys and 160 girls aged 12-18 years old, who replied to a questionnaire and the results showed that the scientific community should continue studying SN, but separating them from the rest of the internet and focus on the need of the users to promote themselves.

Key words: Social Networks, children, adolescents, self-promoting

Introduction

It is undeniable that internet has changed the way which our societies communicate, process information and socialize. In particular, today's youth has never known a

world without internet, a fact that we need to take into account every time we try to make comparisons between pre and after internet era generations. Internet is not just another tool in peoples' social communication toolbox, it is the tool².

Social Networks (S.N.) have been in our lives for over twenty years. The last ten, in fact, are an integral part of our daily activities and the most common activity of children, adolescent and young people, without neglecting that nowadays older people use began using them increasingly. Therefore, SN have fired the curiosity at first, and then attracted the growing interest of the scientific society during the last decade. The interest is increasing as we are sensing the constant changes and the growing numbers of their users. The users are now millions, which make SN able to influence social structures, institutions and the relations that rule them, in a way that we could say that the world is under re-negotiation.

Over the years, various definitions have been proposed for SN, some of them general and some of them not, but to all of them the main core remains the same: interactions in some way. For example, Griffiths and Kuss (2011)³ define virtual communication as social networks where users can create individual profiles, interact with friends and get to know other people with common interests. A more recent –and clearly more comprehensive– definition considers any website that allows you to have social interactions as being a social network⁴.

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² Griffiths, M., D. (2000). Excessive internet use: Implications for sexual behavior. *Cyber Psychology and Behavior*, 3, 537-552.

³ Griffiths, M., D., & Kuss, D., J. (2011). Adolescent social networking: should parents and teachers be worried? *Education and Health*, Vol. 29, No 2.

⁴ Tartari, E. (2015). Benefits and risks of children and adolescents using social media. *European Scientific Journal*, Vol.11, No 13.

One point that emerges from recent studies and opinions around the subject and it's worth mentioning here, is the fact that any derisive statement of the type "positive-negative" must be avoided, since the determining factor in the relationship is the individual and not SN. SN are neutral. Besides, SN are now not only integral, but obviously irreplaceable part of modern societies, and since we have tried the two opposite poles theory before (during the good-bad internet discussion) we know in advance where it ends: somewhere between the pros and cons.

To cut short, what researchers have succeeded to demonstrate beyond any doubt, is how popular SN are. But although the numbers can be overwhelming, whether their use –even overuse- is causing a real problem or at least a problem that derives entirely from them, has not as yet been adequately demonstrated⁵.

So far there have been a number of reasons as to why young people are using the internet, but considering that SN have the same rules and laws or their users have the same motives, might be a mistake. SN are a different system and –now- a culture. For example, international bibliography cites as core-causes and motivations for internet use the following:

- a. Search and maintain contacts and coherence
- b. Search for solutions or answers for personal matters

- c. Search for an escape from routine and/or reality
- d. Management of difficulties and emotions
- e. Negotiation and development of identity
- f. Education-Study

The discussion as to whether SN are used for the same reasons is very wide and it is impossible to do it here. It is worth mentioning, however, that Facebook, YouTube and Wikipedia are considered as SN, despite the fact that it is not hard to understand that between these applications are significant and substantive differences and they are not under the same principles.

In any way, the new generation is born and grow "networked", meaning that they don't need to discover and learn how to live with SN, because they are born with them and in them⁶. What is now certain, is that these "instruments" no longer cause consternations, panic or anxiety, nor they are considered terra incognita, full of monsters and danger. This changes a lot, both reasons and approach and perhaps this alone is enough to bring the scientific community back to the study of SN with different approaches and clearly, different questions.

On a theoretical level, the widespread use of SN by all ages and/or vocations (children and parents, teachers and students, managers and staff etc.) and regardless the reason behind the use, indicates that the relationship between the user and the SN has been re-defined. For example, up to 2009 the internet was the playground of teenagers and young people, with users percentages climbing up to

⁵ Griffiths and Kuss. ο.π.

⁶ Τσίτσικα, Α., & Γιωτάκος, Ο. (2015). Εφηβεία: Οδηγός επιβίωσης. Πεδίο, Αθήνα.

93%, but from 2010 and on, the percentage of adults between 18-29 years old using the internet was roughly equal to that⁷. In a 2010 survey⁸ conducted among children from 8-15 years and 3000 parents, 40% of the girls said that Facebook is the most important thing in their lives, while only a 6% of the boys gave the same answer. According to Eurostat, in Cyprus, the percentage of Greek-Cypriots using SN was 79% in 2016, the fourth largest in Europe and above countries such as France, UK and Germany.

The purpose of this study is to re-approach the subject of SN use and to investigate whether children and adolescents in Cyprus continue to use them for the same reasons mentioned in the bibliography, or not. Although many studies have been carried out on the relationship between children and adolescents and SN, in Cyprus the research is very limited and therefore for our research purposes we assume that this relationship was and is the same or similar to the other European countries. Finally, this study considered only those platforms and applications which are clearly SN, such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, SnapChat etc. Therefore, the relationship between SN and education was not investigated. As far as education is concerned, research shows that young people do not regard SN as educational, but rather as a distraction to their education.

Methodology

Sample

The sample of the study was 261 individuals, residing permanently in Cyprus, ages 12-18

years old and maintaining one or more accounts in various SN. Specifically, 101 boys and 160 girls took part and their demographic data are listed in table 1.

Table 1

Gender		
	N=261	%
M	101	38.7
F	160	61.3
Age		
	N=261	%
12-15	60	23
16-18	201	77

As we see, 93,1% stated that he/she maintains more than one accounts in SN and 95% that he/she access these accounts via mobile phone. As regards the use of SN in hours, the majority (44,8%) stated that he/she uses them for 1-3 hrs daily, 35,6% for 4-6 hrs daily, while a 19,5% stated that he/she uses SN for more than 6 hrs daily.

Tools

For the purposes of the study, a questionnaire was conducted, which required demographic information, information about the length of use and the way of access and 15 items (5 items on the communication, 5 items on the avoidance-security subject and 5 items on self-esteem and self-promotion.

The participants were invited to decide on a four-point Likert scale and the construction of the questionnaire was based on international studies conducted in other countries. The questionnaire was uploaded in

⁷ Lenhart, et al. (2010). Social Media and Mobile Internet use among teen and young adults. Washington DC.

⁸ Coughlin, S. (2010). Facebook is a major influence on girls. BBC News, May 8, BBC.co.uk.

various SN and was sent to various accounts and the only limitations in order to take part in the study were the age and the country of living of the participants.

As regards the processing of the data collected, it was considered interesting to investigate whether there is a statistically significant difference between the averages of the participants, both in terms of gender and age. For the acceptance or rejections of each hypothesis, a t-test for independent samples was conducted.

Results

Daily use of SN

The majority of the participants (44.8%) stated that they use SN for 1-3 hrs daily, 35.6% for 4-6 hrs daily and 19.5% for over 6 hrs daily. In order to examine the hypothesis whether there is a statistically significant difference between the median of boys ($m=1,5842$) and girls ($m=1,8500$), the t-test showed that there is ($p=0,006$), with the girls being more positive. The examinations as to whether the age is also a distinctive factor ($m=2,000$ [a] | $m=1,671$ [b]) the difference also found to be statistically significant ($p=0,003$), therefore both gender and age appear to play an important role as regards the daily time consumed by SN.

Communication and SN

As regards the items concerning communication in SN, for example if the individuals use SN for communication purposes more than any other reason, it appears that this is not the case. In particular, 75,5% stated that they don't use SN to come into contact with people who do not know in

person. The t-test showed that there is a statistically significant difference between boys ($m=2,8416$) and girls ($m=3,0375$) with the girls being more positive ($p=0,031$).

Other items concerning communication, such as whether it is easier to communicate through SN with people they don't know well or if they discuss personal matters in the SN more often than in person or if they facilitate communication with older people, the general response was negative. Table 2 summarizes the results of the answers relating to communication and the relative rates of responses. As regards any statistically significant differences, the test did not show any, either in terms of gender or age, leading to the conclusion that generally, SN are not primarily used for communication.

Table 2

Question	+	-
I use Social Networks to contact...	24,5%	75,5%
Communication is easier...	40,2%	59,8%
I discuss personal matters...	30,6%	69,3%
I communicate easier with older persons...	24,1%	75,8%
Social Networks make dialogue easier...	32,2%	67,8%

Avoidance-Safety and SN

As regards the items relating to avoidance-safety, for example whether SN are an escape from reality, from difficulties and frustrations and whether users are less hurt by rejection or negative treatment, the general response was also negative. The 53,6% stated that rejection hurts, regardless of whether it happens in SN, while 58,6% stated that negative comments in SN hurt the same. In order to test the

hypothesis whether there are statistically significant differences between gender and age, it was found that there is a difference only in terms of gender ($p=0,011$), with the girls being more sensitive than boys.

Self-promotion and SN

The results showed positive trends in the items relating to self-promotion. The 72,5% stated that their self-confidence is stimulated and feel good with themselves when they receive a positive feedback on a post. At approximately same levels (71,6%) the individuals stated that they feel good when they get a positive feedback and a like in a photo they upload and they repeat the process because of it.

According to the above, 74,7% considers that the persona presented in SN reflects their personality, while 72,4% feels happy when they receive positive feedback, regardless the type of their post. In the relevant test, it was found that there is a statistically significant difference in gender ($p=0,014$) with boys showing a more positive attitude than girls.

Table 3 (t-test for independent samples)

Boys Vs Girls
Daily use of SN

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	p-value (two tailed)
Male	101	1.5842	.72481	0.005**
Female	160	1.8500	.77053	
Total	261			

** $p<0,01$

Boys Vs Girls
Contacting people they have never met

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	p-value
Male	101	1.5842	.72481	0.005**
Female	160	1.8500	.77053	
Total	261			

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	p-value (two tailed)
Male	101	2.8416	.70332	0.031*
Female	160	3.0375	.71715	
Total	261			

* $p<0,05$

Boys Vs Girls
Rejection don't hurt as much in the SN

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	p-value (two tailed)
Male	101	2.4455	.83036	0.011*
Female	160	2.7188	.84057	
Total	261			

* $p<0,05$

Boys Vs Girls
If I receive positive comments I feel good about myself

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	p-value (two tailed)
Male	101	2.3663	.73106	0.014*
Female	160	2.1500	.65589	
Total	261			

* $p<0,05$

Discussion

The purpose of this study was a re-approach between SN and the reasons why children and adolescents in Cyprus use them today. The process of the data collected from 261 individuals was very interesting and demonstrates some differentiation from the entrenched idea as regards the use of SN up to the recent past.

International studies agree that there is a differentiation between SN and the rest of the internet, since SN provide a variety of ways of interaction⁹, but it seems that the ages we

⁹ Abdulwahaab, A. (2016). Investigating the impact of social media students. Cardiff Metropolitan University.

study here are now more concerned with the type of interaction linked to self-promotion and not communication. According to the results and in terms of communication, this is not the reason these ages use SN and they don't use them for information either, as this is achieved by purely informative websites such as inline newspapers, sports sites etc.

What matters most is the fact that children and adolescent today seek mostly self-promotion and thus the stimulation of their self-esteem. As regards the relationship between self-esteem and SN is now well documented in international literature. The feedback from online "friends" influences the quality of life and self-esteem to a large extent¹⁰. Diversification today seems to lie in the fact that this particular reason-motivation is more important than any other.

This finding agrees with the findings of other researchers which show that most adolescents and pre-teens of ages 13-17 years old prefer to communicate face to face and many feel that SN are a barrier to this interaction¹¹. It, therefore, makes sense if we move away from the element of communication in the classic sense of the term and believe that SN are now used primarily for other reasons, such as self-promotion.

The reasons this is happening are various and for the sake of discussion we will mention those considered important and consistent with the way of life of young people and the influences of SN and the internet. For

example, today, access to these networks and the promotion of online personas is very easy, due to the use of mobile phones and mobile internet. The ages specified here, in their majority own a smart phone, which they use to access their profile in SN from anywhere and at any time, to the extent that they perceive the term "smart phone" as "access to SN"¹².

Apart from this, SN infiltrate newscasts, game shows etc., where everything also acquires a social persona and where we experience more projection and less information, sometimes for fun, sometimes because it is the new trend and sometimes because this just...sells well. Moreover, we must not underestimate the fact that young people have now direct access through SN to celebrities or models and interact with them, therefore it is possible that this is one more reason for the shift towards self-promotion in SN. For many, SN are the way to the dream, where anyone can be famous and loved.

As far as the online persona is concerned, it seems that young people have no longer the need to adopt one (at least one that deviates to a great extent from their reality). Previously, they were adopting other social identities on internet, in order to express or increase self-esteem, and to enjoy a sense of success¹³. Obviously, this is not considered necessary today.

Finally, any gender differences must not surprise us, since it is obvious that SN are more important to girls, which, compared to

¹⁰ Valkenburg, P., M., Peter, J., & Schouten, A., B. (2006). Friend networking sites and their relationship to adolescents' well-being and social self-esteem. *Cyber Psychology and Behaviour*, 9, 584-590.

¹¹ Rideout, V. (2012). Social Media, Social Life: How teens view their digital lives. *Common Sense Media*. New York.

¹² Rideout, V. (2012). ó.π.

¹³ Widyanto, L., & Griffiths, M., D. (2006). Internet addiction: Does it really exist? Psychology and the internet: Intrapersonal, Interpersonal and Transpersonal applications. NY Academic Press.

boys, have better social skills. If we translate this into online behavior, it is expected that girls use SN more than boys, while boys prefer other online activities, such as playing games. Girls also have deeper sensitivity in SN, but this difference is not always statistically significant, unchanged or decisive.

Conclusion

In essence, SN will be of interest for many years and it is a challenge for us to answer the question whether SN evolve with people or people evolve with SN. For sure they will keep playing an increasingly important role in social life, regardless the age.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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